

Figure S1. Blox-plot graph displaying the value of a pregnancy (€) for cows (n = 4,255) that were eligible for insemination stratified by farm. Estimates for the value of a pregnancy were derived from 10 German dairy farms using the COWVALUE module from DairyComp (Valley Agricultural Software, Tulare, California). Milk price was fixed at 0.35 €/ kg. Other input parameters were: Discount rate = 10%; heifer costs = 1,900 €; maintenance feed costs = 1.50 €; marginal feed costs = 6.40 €; cull value = 600 €.